

Dynamic Monte Carlo Neutron Transport for Molten Salt Reactor Transient Analysis

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ABSTRACT

The Molten Salt Reactor (MSR) is one of the advanced reactor concepts that utilizes liquid molten salt as a fuel. The use of liquid fuel presents a challenge in MSR core analysis due to delayed neutrons' migration. iMC, the Monte Carlo code developed at KAIST, previously established some methods to handle the unique behavior of the MSR. However, the studies focused on the steady-state solution, while transient analysis is crucial for simulating accident scenarios. This study focuses on the development and implementation of Dynamic Monte Carlo (DMC) for time-dependent MSR analysis. The DMC is a well-known scheme used for time-dependent Monte Carlo neutron transport. Nevertheless, the conventional DMC cannot be directly applied to the MSR for delayed-neutron precursor treatment. This study provides the theoretical basis of the MSR-specialized DMC. Also, its computational implementation is studied. A simple 2D graphite-moderated MSR model is suggested to test the MSR DMC. A null transient is performed, clearly showing that the DMC modification works properly for the MSR. The DMC for the MSR is expected to provide an accurate solution for time-dependent situations, thereby aiding in MSR design and licensing.

Keywords: Molten Salt Reactor, Monte Carlo, Transient, Dynamic Monte Carlo, Delayed Neutron Precursor

1. INTRODUCTION

The Molten Salt Reactor (MSR) is a Gen-IV reactor concept that offers significant potential benefits in safety, sustainability, and performance. Unlike conventional solid-fuel reactors, MSRs utilize a liquid molten salt mixture that serves as both the fuel and the coolant. This unique design choice introduces complicated physical phenomena in the current scope of light-water reactors.

A critical challenge stemming from this liquid fuel is the transport of delayed neutron precursors (DNPs). In a traditional reactor, DNPs remain stationary until their emission of the delayed neutron. In the MSRs, however, these precursors are transported with the fuel flow, circulating through the reactor core and the external primary loop. This DNP drift has a direct and significant impact on reactor kinetics as delayed neutrons emitted outside the active core are effectively lost from the fission chain. Thus, migration of the DNP leads to a reduction of the effective delayed neutron fraction β_{eff} and reactor reactivity. This makes high-fidelity transient analysis essential for the robust safety assessment and design of these systems.

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The Monte Carlo neutron transport method is the most accurate approach for reactor core analysis, because it avoids the approximations used in deterministic codes. The Monte Carlo method also supports transient analysis using the Predictor-Corrector Quasi-Static (PCQS) and Dynamic Monte Carlo (DMC) methods. PCQS-MC is a hybrid approach that factorizes the neutron flux into an amplitude function, solved using point kinetics, and a shape function, updated by a fixed-source Monte Carlo calculation. While this method is efficient compared to others, factorization may fail in the face of drastic changes, which can occur in accidental situations. Recalling MSR's liquid fuel, the change in the shape function can be more extreme.

The DMC method, on the other hand, solves the time-dependent transport equation directly by adding a temporal dimension to the simulation. In this approach, both prompt neutrons and delayed neutron precursors are explicitly tracked as particles in time. This methodology inherently accounts for the time-dependent behavior of the neutron population without requiring the calculation of kinetic parameters. Despite the method being computationally expensive, the DMC is often considered the reference solution to transient behavior.

The iMC code, a continuous-energy Monte Carlo neutron transport code developed at the Korea Advanced Institute of Science and Technology (KAIST), has been extensively developed to support high-fidelity reactor analysis. The code features capabilities for transient analysis, based on both PCQS-MC and DMC methods [1]. Moreover, previous studies from the iMC code focused on the MSR analysis, including DNP tracking [2], multiphysics [3], and depletion with nuclide removal [4].

This work focuses on implementing and applying the DMC method within the iMC framework for the transient analysis of MSRs. In this study, a dynamic Monte Carlo methodology is modified for MSR transient analysis and implemented in the iMC code. This modification focuses on integrating the explicit DNP convection with the time-dependent particle transport algorithm. Section 2 will cover the theory behind modifying the DMC for MSRs. Section 3 will then hold the practical implementation of this scheme within the iMC code. Finally, Section 4 will present a simple null transient problem to test and verify the performance of the modified scheme.

2. THEORY

2.1. Molten Salt Reactor Steady-State Analysis

A steady-state solution of the molten salt reactor has been studied. Major modification for the MSR is its delayed neutron precursor movement. The governing equation for MSR can be expressed in terms of neutron flux and precursor distribution. For neutron flux ϕ , the time-dependent equation can be written as below:

$$\frac{1}{v} \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial t} + \vec{\Omega} \cdot \nabla \phi + \Sigma_t \phi = \int \int dE' d\vec{\Omega}' (\chi_p (1 - \beta) \nu \Sigma_f + \Sigma_s) \phi(E', \vec{\Omega}') + \frac{1}{4\pi} \sum_{i=\text{delayed}} \chi_{a,i} \lambda_i C_i. \quad (1)$$

The equation contains a source term from delayed neutron production. The DNP concentration C_i is governed by:

$$\frac{\partial C_i}{\partial t} + \vec{U} \cdot \nabla C_i = -\lambda_i C_i + \int \int dE' d\vec{\Omega}' \beta_i \nu \Sigma_f \phi. \quad (2)$$

For static fuel, Eq. (2) can be analytically obtained and replaces delayed neutron term in Eq. (1).

$$C_i = \frac{\beta_i}{\lambda_i} \int \int dE' d\vec{\Omega}' \beta_i \nu \Sigma_f \phi \rightarrow \chi_{a,i} \lambda_i C_i = \chi_{a,i} \beta_i \int \int dE' d\vec{\Omega}' \beta_i \nu \Sigma_f \phi. \quad (3)$$

The term can be tallied on-the-fly with the neutron cross-section. Therefore, the delayed neutron spectrum and fractions are all required to obtain the delayed neutron source term. However, by introducing flow profile \vec{U} , the steady-state expression is no longer applicable. Instead, the steady-state satisfies:

$$\lambda_i C_i + \vec{U} \cdot \nabla C_i = \int \int dE' d\vec{\Omega}' \beta_i v \Sigma_f \phi. \quad (4)$$

To handle the precursor equation, DNP tracking is simulated based on the relevant factors, similar to the Lagrangian Particle Transport (LPT) method. Given a precursor group, the precursor lifetime can be sampled based on the exponential decay:

$$T_{lifetime} = -\frac{\ln \gamma}{\lambda} \quad (5)$$

where γ and λ are uniform random number and the decay constant of the precursor, respectively. The precursor's position is simulated on-the-fly using the flow profile \vec{U} .

2.2. Dynamic Monte Carlo

The steady-state Monte Carlo obtains reactor parameters by solving the neutron transport equation directly. Tallies, including an eigenvalue, can be obtained from the steady-state Monte Carlo solution. However, for the time-dependent Monte Carlo method, a different approach is required compared to the steady-state method. Since the neutron speed is finite, roughly 2,200 m/s for thermal, the time-of-flight should be considered. In addition, delayed neutrons are generated from their precursors' decay. Time-dependent behaviors should be accurately modeled to assess reactor transients, especially during accident scenarios.

Dynamic Monte Carlo is a time-dependent Monte Carlo scheme that directly accounts for time-dependent effects, including neutron migration and DNP decay. Sjenitzer [5] proposed various schemes for DMC analysis, which is considered the conventional approach to DMC simulation, including forced-decay and branchless reactions.

2.3. Delayed neutron precursor groups in MSR

In addition, Sjenitzer applied a condensed group approach for efficiency. The approach replaces the typical 6 or 8 delayed neutron groups with a single condensed group with a statistical approach. The group g precursor balance and steady-state solution in the static fuel can be expressed group-wise:

$$\frac{dC_g}{dt} = -\lambda_g C_g + \beta_g v \Sigma_f \phi \rightarrow C_{g,steady-state} = \frac{\beta_g}{\lambda_g} v \Sigma_f \phi \quad (6)$$

Therefore, in steady-state, the fraction of each group is proportional to β_g/λ_g . The fraction can be obtained immediately after fission and remains unchanged during the transient simulation. On the other hand, according to Eq. (2), the DNP concentration cannot be analytically determined. Thus, the analytic expression of the group-wise fractions is also unavailable. This leads to an imbalance in the case of the condensed group approach, since the group-wise fraction is unknown after the DNP transport. Abuqudaira et al. [6] also demonstrated that the condensed delayed neutron group introduces a non-negligible bias in both steady-state and transient analyses. Instead, the modified scheme samples the delayed neutron group when the precursor is produced. This may degrade computing efficiency, but it provides an unbiased approach. The approach samples the delayed-neutron group and maintains the group index throughout the calculation.

3. IMPLEMENTATION

3.1. Delayed Neutron Precursor Treatment

3.1.1. DMC initialization

DMC is initialized from the steady-state converged source term. Unlike a conventional eigenvalue problem, which needs a fission source distribution for each cycle, the DMC requires prompt neutron and delayed neutron precursor distributions. In static fuel DMC, the prompt neutron source n and the delayed neutron precursor source of delayed group g , C_{g0} can be expressed with the collision estimator:

$$n = \frac{1}{v} \frac{1}{\Sigma_t} w, C_{g0} = \frac{\beta_g}{\lambda_g} \frac{v \Sigma_f}{\Sigma_t} w \quad (7)$$

where w is a neutron weight collided. For flowing fuel, the DNP tally scheme differs slightly. When the precursor is produced, its position is adjusted according to the steady-state DNP tracking scheme. The precursor is banked as in Eq. (6), but with a shifted position. The scheme is equivalent to the steady-state scheme, which directly tracks the DNP position based on the sampled emission time.

One difference from the steady-state is the treatment of out-of-core precursors. During steady-state analysis, ex-core DNPs are excluded from the calculation because of their negligible contribution to the fission chain. On the other hand, out-of-core DNPs may re-enter the active core through the bottom, thereby affecting the fission chain during the time-dependent analysis.

Instead of excluding the out-of-core contribution, the out-of-core precursor is also banked, as it may contribute to the fission chain when it recirculates back. For the steady-state analysis, a recirculation time is used to determine the reentrance of escaped DNPs. Nevertheless, the approach is inappropriate in time-dependent analysis, as residence time is not constant due to changes in fuel flow speed. Therefore, the ex-core precursor is represented with two quantities: ex-core length, which is steady, and speed, which is adjustable during the transient. The quantities transform the simple time-based approach into a 1D problem. The approach extends the top of the active core with the 1D region, simplifying the out-of-core region. A convenient approach is to set the ex-core speed to the inlet speed boundary condition. The ex-core position is set to zero if the DNP is inside the active core. When the DNP reaches the top of the active core, the ex-core position of the precursor is set to l_{ex} :

$$l_{ex} = v_{ex} T_{recirc} \quad (8)$$

As time elapsed by Δt , the ex-core position reduces by $v_{ex} \Delta t$. When the ex-core position becomes zero, the DNP is considered to have re-entered the active core and continues its tracking. During the steady-state analysis, DNPs are tracked in the 1D extension and excluded from the fission chain if they emit neutrons inside the extension.

3.1.2. Migration of delayed neutron precursor

Starting from the steady-state solution, prompt neutrons are transported until their calculation is terminated or reaches the time boundary. The delayed neutrons need to be sampled from their precursors. The decay scheme follows Sjentizer's approach, except that the DNP group is pre-determined. Note that the DNP position is perturbed when emitting the delayed neutrons.

When the delayed neutrons are sampled, the DNP position is updated based on the fuel flow. According to the forced decay, every DNPs emit a delayed neutron every timestep. Considering the time bin $[t_0, t_1]$, and suppose that the DNP emits the delayed neutron at time $t \in [t_0, t_1]$. First, the delayed neutron emission site migrated from the DNP position at time t_0 , with the time difference $t-t_0$.

The DNP position at time t_i is then updated. The delayed neutrons are excluded as done in the steady-state, when the ex-core position is non-zero. During transport, the precursor's weight decays exponentially based on its decay constant.

During the DMC simulation, additional DNPs are generated from fission reactions. During the DMC simulation between t_0 and t_i , the new DNP produced at time t is shifted by $t_i - t$, with proper consideration of its decay. The overall scheme and the balance can be expressed as follows.

Fig. 1. Population balance between time t_0 and t_i

4. NUMERICAL RESULT

4.1. Problem Description

4.1.1. 2D Molten Salt Reactor Model

Fig. 2. Side view of 2D MSR model (not to scale)

The 2D MSR model, suggested by Pfahl et al. [7], is solved with the modified MSR DMC scheme. The model was presented and solved previously to verify the iMC-OpenFOAM coupled approach [2].

The model is composed of FUNaK fuel channel and graphite moderator. For graphite, thermal scattering data is utilized to accurately analyze the graphite-moderated system. In terms of fuel, its density is set to be a linear to the temperature change:

$$\rho(T) = (5000 - T[K])kg \cdot m^{-3} \quad (9)$$

The temperature and density distributions are applied to the iMC calculation on a mesh-wise basis. The mesh equally subdivides fuel and moderator into 1250 meshes each (50 axial, 25 radial).

In previous studies on iMC-OpenFOAM coupled analysis, a converged state was used: for the null transient, these distributions of temperature, density, and flow velocity are used. Converged solution's eigenvalue is 0.99660 ± 5 .

4.1.2. Calculation condition

For Monte Carlo analysis, 1,000,000 histories per cycle and 20 inactive cycles are used to obtain an initial state for the dynamic analysis. After convergence of the fission source, the DMC calculation is initialized with a timestep of 0.01 seconds. The current study focuses solely on neutronics behavior, so it excludes any thermal feedback from OpenFOAM. The initial power is set to 0.35 MWth, and the MC normalization factor is calculated at the first timestep.

For the neutron cross-section library, ENDF/B-VII.1 is utilized. Also, fission heating data used for delayed photon treatment are from the same library. Regarding the photon transport, the MCPLIB84 cross-section library is used. The power distribution is tallied with both neutron and photon transports. Note that the photons are transported every timestep due to their high speed. In this paper, the delayed photon contribution is considered alongside prompt photon production.

The steady-state eigenvalue of the reactor is 0.99660, leading to a decrease in power and prompt neutrons. For the null transient, the steady-state reactor is forced to be critical by adjusting the neutron yield as follows:

$$v' = v \frac{1}{k_{eff}} = \frac{1}{0.99660} v \rightarrow k_{eff} \sim 1.0 \quad (10)$$

4.2. Result

4.2.1. Neutron-Precursor Balance

During the null transient analysis, we expect the steady-state solution to be preserved throughout the simulation. For the first timestep, from the steady-state solution to 0.01 seconds, the balance between the prompt neutrons, in-core delayed, and ex-core delayed neutron precursor populations is depicted in Fig. 3. In terms of in-core DNPs, escaping precursor weights are larger than incoming. However, since production from the fission chain exceeds decay losses, the imbalance is compensated. Regarding the ex-core precursor, its decay loss is compensated by precursors escaping from the active core.

Fig. 3. Population balance at initial timestep (0.01 seconds)

The imbalance in Fig. 3 arises from statistical uncertainty. For prompt neutrons, because their population is heavily dependent on tracking and reactions, their population and tallies are statistically uncertain. Table I shows the maximum and minimum in-core and ex-core DNP populations throughout the DMC simulation, and their deviation from the initial value.

Table I. In-core and ex-core DNP populations

DNPs	Initial	Max.	Min.
In-core	545,147.2	545,741.3 (+0.10 %)	544,396 (-0.13 %)
Ex-core	453,939.9	453,952.4 (+0.0027 %)	452,736 (-0.26 %)

4.2.2. Time-dependent Quantities

Figure 4 denotes power, precursor, and neutron population evolution during the null transient. In terms of total power, despite statistical fluctuations, it remains within the initial 0.35 MWth. Since the analysis is without temperature feedback, the preservation implies that the neutron population is also conserved. Other quantities, including in-core and ex-core precursor balance, are conserved throughout the simulation.

Fig. 4. Evolution of quantities during null transient.

4.2.3. Computing Time

Table II shows computing time required for single Monte Carlo cycle in steady-state, and single timestep, 0.01 seconds, in transient analysis: DMC and fluid dynamics, respectively. The calculation is performed on 200 cores of Intel(R) Xeon(R) Gold 6148 CPU @ 2.40GHz.

Table II. Comparison of computing time in steady-state and DMC analysis

Calculation	Single MC cycle	Single timestep, DMC	Single timestep, CFD
Computing time [s]	643.9	1126.2	12

5. CONCLUSION

This paper suggests an accurate time-dependent core analysis method for the molten salt reactors, based on the dynamic Monte Carlo DMC. The standard DMC scheme is modified for MSR analysis by incorporating delayed-neutron precursor tracking, with a group-wise DNP approach and time-dependent tracking. The MSR DMC scheme is applied to the 2-dimensional thermal MSR model. Preliminary null transient result shows that the balance between neutrons and precursors is conserved.

Time-dependent analysis of molten salt reactors is crucial for the MSR design. Currently, most time-dependent analyses rely on deterministic methods, such as point kinetics. As they are often based on the assumption of no or slow change in the shape function, an accurate time-dependent approach is necessary. This work is expected to play a vital role in simulating transient behavior, particularly in accident scenarios with radical changes. In addition, the DMC solution is considered the reference due to its high accuracy. The establishment of the MSR-specialized DMC scheme will contribute to the development of MSR neutronics codes by providing the reference solution.

For future studies, coupling with external features and codes will be performed. This includes the OpenFOAM computational fluid dynamics code and the iMC code's internal depletion feature. This will enable highly accurate simulations for accidental situations. Furthermore, the research will focus on accurately modeling the decay of DNPs. The DNP groups in the Monte Carlo simulation are often 6 or 8 groups, gathered with DNPs with similar decay constants. However, similar to the condensed group approach, the multigroup approach may not be valid for the MSR application. Accurate modelling of the DNP will be conducted based on the depletion feature.

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